

The Impacts of Covid-19 on the Event Sector in the Eastern Zone of São Paulo

Os Impactos da Covid-19 no Setor de Eventos na Zona Leste de São Paulo

Los Impactos de la Covid-19 en el Sector de Eventos en la Zona Este de São Paulo

Recebido

Received

Recibido

03 mai. 2025

May. 03, 2025

03 may. 2025

Aceito

Accepted

Aceptado

24 ago. 2025

Aug. 24, 2025

24 ago. 2025

Publicado

Published

Publicado

01 out. 2025

Oct. 01, 2025

01 oct. 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN

2965-3339

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.20167601

São Paulo

v. 4 | n. 1

v. 4 | i. 1

e41345

Outubro/Dezembro

October/December

Octubre/Diciembre

2025

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Abstract:

This study investigated the impacts caused by the Covid-19 pandemic on the events sector in the Eastern Zone of São Paulo city. The relevance of this topic lies in the economic and social importance of the sector, which generates numerous direct and indirect jobs. The main objective was to understand how companies in this field remained active during the pandemic, despite the challenging and unstable context. Quantitative field research was conducted through standardized questionnaires applied to 21 local companies. The results showed that most businesses experienced a considerable drop in revenue but adopted alternative measures such as online events and stronger customer relationships. It is concluded that although the pandemic deeply affected the sector, it also revealed its resilience and adaptive capacity. Nevertheless, reinforcing strategic planning and innovation is essential for dealing with future crises.

Keywords: *pandemic; events sector; Eastern Zone; reinvention; logistics management.*

Resumo:

O presente estudo investigou os impactos causados pela pandemia da Covid-19 no setor de eventos na Zona Leste da cidade de São Paulo. Justifica-se pela relevância econômica e social que esse segmento possui, sendo responsável por gerar empregos diretos e indiretos. O objetivo principal foi compreender de que forma as empresas do setor conseguiram manter-se ativas durante o período pandêmico, mesmo diante de um cenário adverso e instável. Para isso, foi realizada uma pesquisa de campo com abordagem quantitativa, por meio da aplicação de questionários a 21 empresas da região. Os resultados apontaram que a maioria das empresas sofreu significativa redução de faturamento, mas encontrou alternativas para continuar operando, como a adoção de eventos online e a melhoria no relacionamento com os clientes. Conclui-se que, embora os impactos tenham sido profundos, o setor demonstrou resiliência e capacidade de adaptação, sendo necessário, no entanto, reforçar estratégias de gestão e inovação para lidar com futuras crises.

Palavras-chave: *Pandemia; Setor de eventos; Zona Leste; reinvenção; gestão logística.*

Resumen:

Este estudio investigó los impactos causados por la pandemia de Covid-19 en el sector de eventos en la Zona Este de la ciudad de São Paulo. La justificación del tema radica en la importancia económica y social de este sector, que genera empleos directos e indirectos. El objetivo principal fue comprender cómo las empresas del

sector lograron mantenerse activas durante el período pandémico, a pesar de un contexto adverso e inestable. Se realizó una investigación de campo con enfoque cuantitativo, mediante la aplicación de cuestionarios a 21 empresas locales. Los resultados indicaron que la mayoría de las empresas experimentaron una reducción significativa de ingresos, pero encontraron alternativas como la realización de eventos en línea y el fortalecimiento de la relación con los clientes. Se concluye que, aunque los impactos fueron profundos, el sector demostró resiliencia y capacidad de adaptación, siendo necesario reforzar las estrategias de gestión e innovación para enfrentar futuras crisis.

Palabras clave: *pandemia; sector de eventos; Zona Este; reinención; gestión logística.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic caused an unprecedented global health and economic crisis, directly affecting various sectors of the economy. The events sector, highly dependent on physical presence and in-person gatherings, was among the most affected, forced to suspend its activities indefinitely.

According to the Brazilian Association of Event Promoters (ABRAPE, 2021), approximately 350,000 events were canceled or postponed between 2019 and 2021, directly affecting the income of millions of professionals, including producers, event planners, waiters, musicians, security personnel, decorators, suppliers, and other service providers. While many economic sectors managed to adapt to the pandemic context through remote work and digitalization, the events sector encountered significant limitations in this transition.

In this context, this study is justified by the need to understand how small and medium-sized enterprises in São Paulo's East Zone events sector faced the challenges posed by the pandemic. This region, characterized by many self-employed entrepreneurs and family businesses, was heavily affected by sanitary restrictions and the drop in demand for social and corporate events.

The general objective of this study is to analyze the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the events sector in São Paulo's East Zone, with an emphasis on the strategies adopted by small and medium-sized enterprises to remain active in the market.

The specific objectives of the study are: i) To describe the concept of events and their economic and social relevance; ii) To demonstrate the importance of logistics management for the realization of events; iii) To identify the main consequences of the pandemic for the events sector; iv) To analyze the prospects for the sector's recovery in the post-pandemic period.

The guiding question of this study is: How did the events sector in the East Zone region of the city of São Paulo remain active in the market during the Covid-19 pandemic?

To address this problem, the research uses a descriptive methodology and a quantitative approach, based on a literature review and the application of a structured questionnaire to 21 companies in the events sector located in the East Zone of São Paulo. The data collection focused on understanding companies' experiences, strategies, and impacts during the pandemic's most critical period.

Therefore, this study seeks to contribute to understanding the organizational behavior of event companies during crises and to support the formulation of more effective strategies for resilience and economic recovery in the sector.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Concept of Events

Events are planned gatherings that bring together people or entities at a location, date, and time, previously organized by qualified professionals, with the goal of promoting celebrations, commercialization, dissemination, and the strengthening of cultural, economic, social, and family ties. An event can generate strong emotions among both

participants and organizers. For participants, it represents an opportunity for interaction, relaxation, and reflection; for organizers, it is a moment to apply knowledge and practical skills, while requiring hard work, concentration, creativity, organization, management, planning, and, above all, results (Zanella, 2006).

In this sense, Salgado (2010) conceptualizes an event in a simple way:

An event is a promotional institutional set, used in targeted communication, with the purpose of creating a concept and establishing the image of organizations, products, services, ideas, and individuals or legal entities, through a previously planned event, occurring in a single space of time, with the interaction between participants, whether physical or through technological resources (SALGADO, 2010, p. 31, our translation).

Events play a significant role in the economy, contributing to job creation and economic activity. They involve various professionals, such as producers, security personnel, musicians, catering suppliers, waiters, decorators, and others, who all contribute to the success of memorable events. It is a team effort, with activities ranging from organization to active participation in the event.

Cleuza G. Gimenes Cesca (2008 sp) highlights that the activity of "event organizer" is not the prerogative of any specific profession but requires training that facilitates entry into this field, which is so relevant to organizations.

Brazilian culture values in-person events such as meetings, weddings, birthdays, conferences, and graduations. However, many professions have had to adapt, reorganize, or pause their activities, requiring professionals to reinvent themselves and demonstrate the ability to create and organize events with limited resources to remain active in the market.

2.2 The Importance of Logistics Management for the Events Sector

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During the pandemic, efficient logistics management became essential for companies' survival, regardless of their segment or size. In the events sector, making sound decisions is crucial, as they help build a solid and promising image for the company.

Logistics plays a fundamental role because, even with meticulous planning, logistical failures can compromise the entire event. Without efficient logistics, it is impossible to hold a memorable event, since the success of an event is intimately linked to logistics, encompassing everything from planning to execution, including the movement of people, communication materials, set up of environments, programming, and other necessary materials.

Simões and Ribeiro (2007, p. 2) state that "the PDCA cycle is one of the quality management tools that seeks to improve results, helping to find the root causes of a problem and drive effective action towards its solution (our translation)". In accordance with the same author, the PDCA cycle consists of four stages: i) Plan: Identifying the problem and establishing objectives for the development of an action plan. ii) Do: Practical implementation of the established action plan. iii) Check: Evaluating the achievement of goals and monitoring the execution of the plan. iv) Act: Making necessary adjustments identified in the process and maintaining continuous improvements.

Source: Simões and Ribeiro (2007)

This tool aims to continuously improve company results by enabling the quick identification and correction of flaws. In the events sector, its application is extremely relevant, as it helps avoid greater losses.

Therefore, a checklist is an indispensable tool for good organization. Each process requires a specific checklist; for example, checking the furniture cannot be done simultaneously with checking the arrival of food, so separate lists are needed to avoid bottlenecks at these stages.

Proper supplier selection is crucial, as unforeseen events can lead to planning setbacks. Having service providers who offer quick, strategic solutions is essential for minimizing potential errors.

When organizing an event, there can be no delays in the delivery of food provided by the catering service, sound equipment, furniture and flower decorations (which are fragile and perishable) provided by decorators, among other things. Hence, detailed planning of the PDCA cycle is essential, as certain requirements must be met on schedule.

Salgado (2010) emphasizes that "when we fail in preparation and planning, we move towards failure in execution." Thus, successful management requires well-structured projects for each event, considering factors such as the audience profile, theme, date, required services and team assembly, among others.

2.3 The consequences of the pandemic for the events sector

The year 2020 surprised all Brazilians, and several professions had to adapt, be rearranged, or even be interrupted, even if only temporarily. The events sector was no different. Professionals in the field had to reinvent themselves to avoid a complete shutdown, even as the events industry was among the most affected during the pandemic.

Social isolation, however challenging it may have been, also served as a catalyst for the pursuit of new knowledge, the unification of the sector in search of greater representation, the adoption of different work practices, and the need to exercise creativity to innovate processes and ensure survival in the new context imposed by the pandemic.

According to Silva (2022), during the worsening of the health crisis, the sector faced

numerous complications, such as the paralysis of events, the drop in revenue, the impossibility of employees being present at their workplaces, and the reduction in demand, among other factors that required concentration and rapid adaptation in the management and control of companies.

[...] more than 350,000 events were canceled in 2020, and another 530,000 were not held this year. The impacts were felt by more than six million people who depended on parties, corporate events, weddings, and shows to survive. Professionals in the field saw their income practically disappear or lost their jobs (EXAME, 2022, SP, our translation).

Events, once seen as tools for various purposes such as learning, networking, promoting products and services, and even social celebrations, have been altered to meet the demands of the moment. Adapting to the new reality was essential, especially for professionals in the sector, who, as Zanella (2012) highlights, have an obligation to execute their projects in a planned manner, with professionalism and competence, to avoid negative repercussions for companies and their audiences.

Before the pandemic, holding in-person events was common, with large gatherings that favored both audience reach and market expansion for companies. The large number of people was characteristic of events ranging from small to large. However, with the restrictions imposed by the pandemic, this dynamic was profoundly altered, impacting not only the number of participants but also the way events were organized and the financial results, which were severely affected by the decrease in the number of events and the adoption of new models, such as hybrid and online events.

2.4 Perspectives on the recovery of the events sector post-pandemic

Despite the gradual recovery and stabilization of the events sector after the pandemic, important challenges and lessons remain. While many economic sectors adapted quickly to remote operations during the health crisis, the events sector was among the most affected, experiencing a sharp drop in demand, rising unemployment, and significant financial losses.

While possible, holding events in a hybrid or remote format did not require large teams. As a result, companies in the sector opted to cut non-essential costs, thereby reducing labor and other operational resources.

With the partial reopening of activities starting in August 2021, even with limitations on audience size and the application of health protocols, the sector began to show some optimism. The gradual resurgence of events has once again generated jobs and income in the region, indicating the beginning of a recovery.

With the experience gained, the events sector now recognizes the importance of maintaining safety and hygiene protocols as part of its standard operating procedures. Adopting good sanitary practices not only strengthens public confidence but also helps prevent future risks to public health. Thus, beyond a temporary need, the precautions learned during the pandemic have become an essential differentiator for ensuring the continuity and credibility of in-person events.

Although the events sector has shown signs of recovery following the pandemic's impact, it still bears significant marks from the period of instability. Many professionals have gradually re-established themselves but remain aware of the sector's vulnerability, often classified as non-essential in crisis situations. The experience has reinforced the

importance of constant preparation and adaptability, which have become fundamental skills for facing unpredictable scenarios and ensuring the sustainability of activities in the future.

2.5 The Events Sector in the Context of the Pandemic

The Covid-19 pandemic triggered one of the biggest health and economic crises in recent history, profoundly impacting sectors that depend on physical presence and social interaction, such as the events industry. According to the Brazilian Micro and Small Business Support Service (SEBRAE, 2020), social isolation led to the immediate paralysis of all nonessential activities. The events sector, which represents approximately 4% of the national GDP, was among the first to shut down and the last to resume operations, incurring estimated losses of R\$ 230 billion between 2020 and 2021 (ABRAPE, 2022).

The work of Abrão Junior and Ferreira (2023) reveals that approximately 97% of entrepreneurs in the study area reported significant losses, leaving many professionals without a source of income for extended periods. This scenario prompted a forced restructuring of the sector and highlighted the urgency of public policies to support its recovery.

2.6 Reinventing Business Processes and Models

One of the specific objectives of this work is to understand how entrepreneurs adapted to the new context. The study by Abrão Junior and Ferreira (2023) shows that reinvention was inevitable and was achieved through initiatives such as the creation of promotional vouchers, the intensive use of social networks, and the offering of events in reduced or online formats. These strategies ensured a degree of continuity in activities even in an extremely adverse scenario.

Business reinvention has become a necessity for maintaining a market presence. Professionals have adopted digital tools, sought new partnerships, and invested in training and development to ensure relevance and appeal to their target audience. These initiatives confirm what Barreto (cited in Schlindwein, 2004) defines as entrepreneurship: "the ability to create and build something from very little or almost nothing".

As Martin and Lisboa (2020) state, the current scenario demands that companies in the events sector quickly adopt strategies to keep pace with ongoing changes. Given this, many of them are forced to define which event model is most suitable for their operations.

The digital transformation of events is a reality that has accelerated in recent years, driven by an increasingly connected, digital audience. In this process of digital transformation, the entire industry faces a decision about the format of its events. Should they be: in-person, hybrid or virtual? (Martin, Lisboa, 2020, p. 3, our translation).

As stated by Priscila Vieira (2020), hybrid events integrate in-person experiences with virtual resources. In both hybrid and digital formats, the key to maintaining the online audience's interest lies in offering highly relevant content, presented in ways that differ from those used in physical meetings.

2.7 Challenges Faced During the Pandemic Period

Another key point is identifying the main challenges faced during the period of social

isolation. As maintained by data collected by Abrão Junior and Ferreira (2023), budget cuts, inventory losses, lack of government support, and legal uncertainty were among the main obstacles reported. Professionals in the sector also faced uncertainty about returning to work and emotional difficulties stemming from economic instability.

Even with the government's emergency aid, many entrepreneurs were unable to access the aid or considered it insufficient to cover their expenses. Law 14.046/2020, which allowed the rescheduling of events without the need for immediate reimbursement, also raised doubts about its application, creating a legal uncertainty that further aggravated the situation.

2.8 Resilience and Survival in Times of Crisis

The pandemic highlighted the need for resilience as an essential skill for professionals in the events sector. Abrão Junior and Ferreira (2023) emphasize that, even in the face of adversity, the interviewees demonstrated strong commitment, grit, and determination to continue their activities, albeit in a partial or adapted manner.

In this context, resilience is understood as the ability to overcome obstacles and find viable alternatives to remain active in the market. This attitude was evident in creative reinvention efforts, the strengthening of the entrepreneurial spirit, and the continuous pursuit of innovation and professional development. Santos and Acosta (2011) reinforce this understanding by stating that the entrepreneur transforms the environment in which they live, even amid chaos and uncertainty.

Resilience can be understood as a dynamic process of interaction between the individual and the environment, reflecting how a person responds to risky situations and maintains their identity even in the face of adversity.

The term resilience in the context of work in organizations refers to the existence – or the construction – of adaptive resources to preserve a healthy relationship between human beings and their work in a changing environment permeated by numerous forms of disruption. Coutu (2002) points out three characteristics of a resilient person or organization: 1) a firm acceptance of reality; 2) a deep belief, generally supported by strongly held values, that life is meaningful; and 3) a “mysterious” ability to improvise. (Barlach, Limongi-França & Malvezzi, 2008, p. 104, our translation).

The study shows that, even without effective government support, professionals sought solutions on their own, demonstrating that individual and collective resilience were decisive factors in remaining in the sector. Social isolation not only imposed barriers but also motivated structural and behavioral changes, essential for survival and recovery in the post-crisis period.

3. METHOD

This study is characterized as applied basic research, with a quantitative approach and a descriptive objective. The method adopted is inductive, as proposed by Marconi and Lakatos (2003), which is structured in three stages: i) observation of phenomena; ii) identification of the relationships between them; and iii) generalization of conclusions. The method was chosen because it allows analysis of a specific phenomenon – the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic – based on empirical observations from a representative sample of the events sector.

Data collection was conducted through field research using a structured questionnaire with objective, closed-ended questions, administered to 21 small- and medium-sized companies operating in the events sector, all located in the East Zone of São Paulo. The selection of companies was based on their direct involvement in organizing and executing social and corporate events.

The data collection period took place between January and March 2022 and focused on understanding the sector's main impacts from the pandemic and the strategies used to cope with the crisis. The data was organized and analyzed using descriptive statistics, with the results presented in illustrative graphs that demonstrate the main trends.

The questionnaire aimed to assess, among other aspects, reductions in company revenue, the adoption of online events, management measures during social isolation, investment in customer relationships, and prospects for resuming in-person activities.

The adopted methodology enabled a concrete, measurable understanding of how companies in São Paulo's East Zone events sector responded to the challenges of the pandemic and which factors were decisive for their continued presence in the market.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and analyzes the results of field research conducted with companies in the events sector in São Paulo's East Zone. The collected data were analyzed in light of the existing literature to understand the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the sector and the strategies adopted to adapt to and recover from it.

To achieve these objectives, four key questions were formulated to guide data collection. The questions addressed fundamental aspects of business management and operations during the pandemic, with an emphasis on analyzing revenue reductions, adopting online events as an alternative for business continuity, maintaining transparent relationships with clients, and investing in corrective measures to mitigate existing problems and prevent further impacts. The questions are presented in a table below for better visualization.

Table 1 – Questions used in the field research

Nº	Tema Investigado	Pergunta Aplicada
1	Reduction in Revenue	Has your company experienced a significant drop in revenue because of COVID-19?
2	Online Event Organization	During the pandemic, did your company switch to organizing events online?
3	Customer Relationship	Did your company adopt a more transparent and responsive relationship with customers during this critical period?
4	Solving Pre-existing Problems	Did your company invest in resolving previous problems to minimize the impact during the pandemic?

Source: Prepared by the authors (2022)

4.1 Data collection

For this study, 21 companies in São Paulo's East Zone, all operating in the events sector, were interviewed. All companies fully responded to the questionnaire, which consisted of closed, objective questions.

During the analysis of the responses, the following relevant points were observed:

Companies were heavily impacted by the pandemic, experiencing significant uncertainty amid shutdowns, event postponements, and cancellations.

With the arrival of COVID-19, 47% of respondents reported a revenue decline of more than 30%. Another 24% indicated a 10% to 30% reduction, as shown in Graph 1.

Chart 1 - Reduction in revenue due to the impact of COVID-19

Source: Prepared by the authors (2022)

The second question related to the organization of online events; the data reveals that 90% of companies managed to adapt to the context of social isolation by holding online events, while 10% did not carry out activities in this format, as highlighted in Graph 2:

Chart 2 - Organizing online events

Source: Prepared by the authors (2022)

All companies (100%) stated that they had adopted a transparent, receptive approach to customer relationships to maintain trust and mitigate the impacts of the period. No graph was created for this question because a graphical illustration of the data with total representativeness (100%) is not justified, given the lack of variation in the responses. Graphical representations are more effective when there is diversity or comparisons to be made. In this case, the data is better understood and conveyed directly through a textual narrative.

The fourth and final question concerns investments to address potential setbacks and problems of greater impact; 86% of managers reported taking advantage of the lockdown period to resolve longstanding issues and restructure internal processes. 14% did not adopt this practice.

Chart 3 - Investment in resolving previous problems to prevent greater impacts

Source: Prepared by the authors (2022)

Thus, in response to the research question: "How did the events sector in the East Zone of São Paulo remain active in the market during the Covid-19 pandemic?", it is concluded that, although heavily affected, companies sought alternatives to continue operating. The use of technology for online events, the adoption of management tools, and the strengthening of customer relationships were essential actions for companies' survival during the most critical period.

Marketing in this context stands out. Companies have come to recognize that transparent, empathetic customer service can build customer loyalty, foster trust, and drive spontaneous referrals, especially during times of crisis. As Kotler and Armstrong state:

Relationship marketing involves creating, maintaining, and strengthening relationships with customers and other stakeholders. [...] Its goal is to offer long-term value to customers, commensurate with their success, and to provide them with long-term satisfaction (Kotler and Armstrong, 1998, p. 397, our translation).

As pointed out by Corrêa and Caon (2002), a satisfied customer becomes a brand advocate, promoting it through spontaneous recommendations, a fundamental aspect for the survival of companies in contexts of uncertainty.

Finally, the data indicate that, faced with an unexpected scenario, companies operating in the events sector needed to anticipate, plan more rigorously, and invest in solutions to ensure their continuity and pave the way for the resumption of activities in the post-pandemic period.

5. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to analyze the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the events sector, with a focus on small and medium-sized enterprises in São Paulo's East Zone. The research sought to understand how these companies maintained their operations during a period marked by severe social and economic restrictions, identifying the strategies they adopted, the challenges they faced, and the results they achieved.

Among the specific objectives, it was possible to: i) describe the concept of events; ii) demonstrate the importance of logistics management for the sector; iii) analyze the consequences of the pandemic; and iv) discuss the prospects for post-pandemic recovery. All these objectives were addressed throughout the work, highlighting the topic's relevance to the fields of administration, economics, and event management.

Based on data collected from interviews with 21 companies, the results indicate that, although the events sector has been profoundly impacted, companies have managed, in part, to adapt to the new scenario through holding online events, adopting management tools such as the PDCA cycle, strengthening customer relationships, and restructuring internal processes. These strategies demonstrate the resilience and capacity for innovation of the professionals involved.

Thus, it can be stated that the events sector has, over time, partially overcome the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the critical moment is in the past, the

crisis's effects persist across various aspects of business management and operations. Companies have demonstrated adaptability and innovation, but full recovery still requires time, investment, and continuous adjustments to consolidate a new, more resilient operating model aligned with the demands of the post-pandemic scenario.

This research also makes relevant contributions to the field of knowledge, especially by illuminating the reality of a segment often neglected in economic and social discussions and by highlighting its importance not only as a generator of entertainment but also as a driver of employment and income.

However, this study has some limitations, including a restricted geographical scope to the East Zone of São Paulo and a small number of participating companies, which limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or the sector.

Therefore, it is suggested that new studies with a broader territorial scope be conducted, encompassing companies of different sizes and regions, to analyze how the events sector has repositioned itself in a post-pandemic context. The adoption of more in-depth qualitative methodologies, such as in-depth interviews or case studies, to reveal nuances in the processes of innovation, digitalization, and continuous adaptation, is also recommended. Furthermore, analyzing financial data across different economic cycles is pertinent, enabling evaluation not only of the pandemic's impact but also of the sector's long-term resilience and preparedness for future crises.

In conclusion, the pandemic imposed unprecedented challenges but also spurred a significant transformation in how events are organized and conceived. The responsiveness, adaptability, and reinvention demonstrated by the companies studied highlight the sector's resilience and serve as a basis for future reflection and strategic planning.

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